

Synthesis and characterization of new *N*-arylsalicylaldiminates of germanium(IV) and tin(IV)

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Abstract : *N*-Arylsalicylaldiminates of germanium(IV) and tin(IV) of the type $MCl_{4-n}(OC_6H_4CH=NAr)_n$, where M = Ge or Sn, $n = 1$ or 2, Ar = $C_6H_2Me_{3-2,4,6}$ or $C_6H_3Pr^i_{2-2,6}$ have been prepared and characterized by elemental analyses, IR and NMR spectral studies, and molecular weight measurements.

Keywords : *N*-Arylsalicylaldiminates, germanium(IV), tin(IV).

During the last four decades, there had been considerable and notable development in the chemistry of metal complexes of Schiff bases and β -ketoamines¹ for several reasons including their structural diversity, importance in biochemical, agricultural, and industrial applications. The last ten years have shown a renaissance of interest in the study of metal complexes of *N*-arylsalicylaldimines² and Schiff base ligands derived from 1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diamine³, with more emphasis on their structural elucidation by X-ray crystallographic studies and applications in catalysis^{3,4} and biomimetic chemistry⁵. There are several interesting features associated with sterically demanding *N*-arylsalicylaldimines. First, these ligands with good π -donor atoms are expected to stabilize higher oxidation states with highly covalent M–O (phenolate) bonds. A second, general reason to study the complexation behaviour of these ligands is the expectation that the attachment of a bulky group such as 2,4,6-trimethylphenyl or 2,6-diisopropylphenyl on azomethine nitrogen atom may be able to inhibit the formation of strong intramolecular N→M dative bond due to steric factors. Third, these ligands commonly improve, thermal stability, volatility and hydrocarbon solubility of metal complexes. This work stems from our continuing interest in the coordination chemistry of ligands containing phenoxo and allied group functionality², and in this paper we report synthesis and characterization of *N*-arylsalicylaldiminate ($OC_6H_4CH=NC_6H_2H_2Me_{3-2,4,6}$ and $OC_6H_4CH=NC_6H_3Pr^i_{2-2,6}$) complexes of germanium(IV) and tin(IV).

Results and discussion

The new *N*-arylsalicylaldiminates of tetravalent ger-

manium and tin have been conveniently synthesized in quantitative yields by the reactions of (i) $GeCl_4$ with $HOC_6H_4CH=NAr$ using pyridine as a proton acceptor [eq. (1)] and (ii) $SnCl_4$ with $NaOC_6H_4CH=NAr$ (Ar = $C_6H_2Me_{3-2,4,6}$ or $C_6H_3Pr^i_{2-2,6}$) [eq. (2)] in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios in benzene.

The new derivative (1-8) (Table 1) are moisture-sensitive, coloured (yellow to reddish-brown) solids having sharp melting points, soluble in typical organic solvents (e.g. benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, dichloromethane), and monomeric ebullioscopically in benzene solution.

Spectroscopic characterization :

As expected infrared absorptions due to OH group in

Table 1. Analytical and some physical data for *N*-arylsalicylaldiminates of germanium(IV) and tin(IV)

Compd. ^a Empirical formula Yield ^b (%), colour	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					M. wt. Found (Calcd.)
		C	H	Ge/Sn	Cl	N	
Cl ₃ Ge(OC ₆ H ₄ CH=NC ₆ H ₂ Me _{3-2,4,6}) (1) C ₁₆ H ₁₆ Cl ₃ GeNO (85), Yellow	62.5	46.10 (46.05)	3.80 (3.86)	17.8 (17.40)	25.6 (25.49)	3.27 (3.36)	420 (417)
Cl ₂ Ge(OC ₆ H ₄ CH=NC ₆ H ₂ Me _{3-2,4,6}) ₂ (2) C ₃₂ H ₃₂ Cl ₂ GeN ₂ O ₂ (82), Light yellow	66	62.10 (61.98)	5.25 (5.20)	11.87 (11.71)	11.37 (11.43)	4.50 (4.52)	635 (620)
Cl ₃ Ge(OC ₆ H ₄ CH=NC ₆ H ₃ Pr ⁱ _{2-2,6}) (3) C ₁₉ H ₂₂ Cl ₃ GeNO (79), Yellow	64	49.72 (49.68)	4.86 (4.83)	15.70 (15.81)	23.9 (23.51)	2.98 (3.5)	465 (459)
Cl ₂ Ge(OC ₆ H ₄ CH=NC ₆ H ₃ Pr ⁱ _{2-2,6}) ₂ (4) C ₃₈ H ₄₄ Cl ₂ GeN ₂ O ₂ (81), Greenish yellow	68	64.86 (64.80)	6.38 (6.30)	10.28 (10.31)	10.13 (10.7)	3.87 (3.98)	708 (704)
Cl ₃ Sn(OC ₆ H ₄ CH=NC ₆ H ₂ Me _{3-2,4,6}) (5) C ₁₆ H ₁₆ Cl ₃ GeNOSn (85), Yellow	70	41.52 (41.47)	3.44 (3.48)	25.73 (25.62)	23.10 (22.95)	2.94 (3.02)	470 (463)
Cl ₂ Sn(OC ₆ H ₄ CH=NC ₆ H ₂ Me _{3-2,4,6}) ₂ (6) C ₃₂ H ₃₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ Sn (80), Yellow	74	57.75 (57.69)	4.82 (4.84)	17.86 (17.82)	10.73 (10.64)	4.08 (4.20)	677 (666)
Cl ₃ Sn(OC ₆ H ₄ CH=NC ₆ H ₃ Pr ⁱ _{2-2,6}) ₂ (7) C ₁₉ H ₂₂ Cl ₃ NOSn (85), Yellow	80–81	45.21 (45.15)	4.36 (4.39)	23.59 (23.49)	21.13 (21.04)	2.66 (2.77)	510 (505)
Cl ₂ Sn(OC ₆ H ₄ CH=NC ₆ H ₃ Pr ⁱ _{2-2,6}) ₂ (8) C ₃₈ H ₄₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ Sn (81), Yellow	85–86	60.78 (60.82)	5.98 (5.91)	15.92 (15.82)	9.50 (9.45)	3.69 (3.73)	760 (750)

^aAll the solids. ^bYield refers to recrystallized product.

the 3150–3500 cm⁻¹ region was found to be absent in the spectra of all these (1–8) compounds. The infrared spectra of all these (1–4) display sharp and intense bands due to νC=N in the 1616–1626 cm⁻¹ region, which is shifted ~6 cm⁻¹ to the higher frequency side with respect to those observed for parent ligands (1610–1620 cm⁻¹)⁶. The intense bands observed in the 892–906 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to νGe–O⁷. Complexes having GeCl₃ and

>GeCl₂ moieties show absorptions at 275, 282 and 283 cm⁻¹, respectively, due to Ge–Cl stretching mode. Tin(IV) complexes (5–8) show bands in the 1238–1300 and 1622–1638 cm⁻¹ regions due to νC–O and νC=N, respectively. These bands show a higher frequency shift of ~30 cm⁻¹ for νC–O^{2f} and ~15 ± 3 cm⁻³ for νC=N,⁶ indicating the coordination of phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen⁶ to the tin(IV) centre. Appearance of medium in-

tensity bands in the 534–540 and 403–426 cm^{-1} regions are ascribable to Sn–O and Sn–N stretching vibrations⁸, respectively. Complexes **6** and **8** exhibit two additional bands due to Sn–Cl stretching vibrations at 325, 371 cm^{-1} (**6**) and 356, 374 cm^{-1} (**8**), respectively, which is similar with that reported earlier for *cis*-Cl₂Sn(acac)₂⁹. Interestingly, derivatives **5** and **7** display bands at 325, 371 and 378 cm^{-1} due to ν Sn–Cl, consistent with the presence of both the *cis* and *trans* chlorine atoms.

The ¹H NMR spectra have the expected pattern characteristic of the Schiff base ligands HOC₆H₄CH=NC₆H₂Me_{3-2,4,6} and HOC₆H₄CH=NC₆H₃Pr_{2-2,6}.

The spectral data for **1–8** are summarized in Table 2 and each proton peak has been assigned. Some noteworthy observations are: (i) signals due to the intramolecularly (O–H...N) and intermolecularly (O–H...O) hydrogen bonded OH group at δ 13.5 of the ligands are absent in the spectra of new compounds, indicating the replacement of OH proton by a metal(loid) atom; (ii) signals observed in the δ 8.40–8.46 region for azomethine proton are either remain unaffected or shifted slightly to higher field with reference to those found for corresponding parent ligand and (iii) the chemical shifts noted for methyl and isopropyl groups attached to the aromatic ring as well as those of the ring protons remain unaffected with reference to those observed for the corresponding ligand.

The ¹³C NMR spectra also have the expected pattern characteristic for the organic ligands. For example, the ¹³C {¹H} NMR spectra of **1–4**, **6** and **8** show signals in the δ 161.28–163.93 (HC=N), 166.3–167.18 (C–O) and 117.28–166.31 (aromatic carbons) regions. The chemical shift values for the aromatic ring carbons are almost similar to those observed for the parent ligands. Interestingly, complexes **6** and **8** show a downfield shift of \sim 2.0 ppm for azomethine carbon signals compared with corresponding signals of the parent ligands. Such a downfield shift for the azomethine carbon in the latter two compounds is more likely due to the formation of a transannular N→Sn dative bond.

The ¹¹⁹Sn NMR data for **5** (δ –416.29) and **7** (δ –452.12) are consistent with pentacoordinate tin(IV) centre, while for derivatives **6** (δ –598.12) and **8** (δ –596.17) tin(IV) is hexacoordinated^{2f,10}.

In view of the above discussion on the basis of IR and NMR spectral data, bidentate (O, N) ligating characteristics of the ligands, and monomeric nature of the complexes **1–8**, the structures **I** and **II** may be proposed for

penta- and hexa-coordinated compounds **1**, **3**, **5**, **7** and **2**, **4**, **6**, **8**, respectively.

M = Ge (**1**) and (**3**);
Sn (**5**) and (**7**)
(I)

M = Ge (**2**) and (**4**);
Sn (**6**) and (**8**)
(II)

Experimental

All reactions and subsequent manipulations were performed under rigorous anhydrous conditions, using oven dried (130–150 °C) glass apparatus fitted with standard interchangeable quickfit joints. Reagent grade (Merck, India) benzene, toluene, *n*-hexane and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were refluxed over sodium benzophenone ketyl and distilled prior to use. GeCl₄ and SnCl₄ were obtained from Aldrich and were freshly distilled prior to use. Dichloromethane, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride were distilled from CaH₂. Ligands HOC₆H₄CH=NC₆H₂Me_{3-2,4,6} and HOC₆H₄CH=NC₆H₃Pr_{2-2,6} were prepared according to the procedure described in our recent publication^{2b}. Melting points were determined on a Toshniwal (India) melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Microanalytical (C, H) analyses were performed by Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre (RSIC), CDRI, Lucknow. IR spectra in the 4000–200 cm^{-1} range were recorded as Nujol mulls on a Perkin-Elmer-557 spectrophotometer. NMR spectra (¹H at 89.55 MHz, ¹³C at 22.49 MHz and ¹¹⁹Sn at 33.35 MHz) were recorded in CDCl₃ solutions on a JEOL FX-90Q spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference, whereas SnMe₄ was used as an external reference for ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra recorded in benzene solution. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in benzene using a Gallenkamp ebulliometer with thermister sensing device. Germanium and tin were determined as oxides (MO₂). Nitrogen and chloride were determined by Kjeldahl and Volhard methods, respectively.

Synthesis of new complexes :

Two different synthetic procedures one for germanium(IV) *N*-arylsalicylaldiminates and the other for tin(IV) analogues were used. For the sake of brevity, preparative details of one typical example of each type is described in the following pages, while analytical and

Table 2. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data (δ, ppm) for *N*-arylsalicylaldiminates (L¹H and L²H) and their derivatives (1-8)

	¹ H	¹³ C
(1)	2.21 (6H, s, Me-9,13), 2.30 (3H, s, Me-11), 6.81-7.21 (4H, m, phenolate-H), 7.26-7.62 (2H, m, aniline-H), 8.42 (1H, s, CH=N), 13.42 (1H, s, OH)	18.36 (C ₉ -Me, C ₁₃ -Me), 20.75 (C ₁₁ -Me), 117.36 (C ₅), 118.36 (C ₃), 127.57 (C ₁₁), 128.87 (C ₄), 131.64 (C ₉ , C ₁₃), 133.58 (C ₁), 145.8 (C ₅), 161.38 (C ₇), 166.25 (C ₂)
(2)	1.21 (12H, d, J 6 Hz, CHMe ₂), 3.02 (2H, sept, J 6 Hz, CHMe ₂), 6.93-7.33 (4H, m, phenolate-H), 7.37-7.64 (3H, m, aniline-H), 8.40 (1H, s, CH=N), 13.04 (1H, s, OH)	23.56 (CHMe ₂), 28.00 (CHMe ₂), 117.49 (C ₅), 118.41 (C ₃), 122.97 (C ₁₁), 125.24 (C ₄), 131.80 (C ₉ , C ₁₃), 132.88 (C ₆), 138.19 (C ₁), 146.37 (C ₈), 161.43 (C ₇), 166.25 (C ₂)
(3)	2.23 (6H, s, Me-9,13), 2.32 (3H, s, Me-11), 6.84-7.23 (4H, m, phenolate-H), 7.26-7.64 (2H, m, aniline-H), 8.45 (1H, s, CH=N)	18.30 (C ₉ -Me, C ₁₃ -Me), 20.69 (C ₁₁ -Me), 117.28-166.31 (aromatic ring carbons), 161.368 (C ₄), 166.31 (C ₂)
(4)	2.19 (12H, s, Me-9,13), 2.32 (3H, s, Me-11), 6.93-7.19 (4H, m, phenolate-H), 7.28-7.59 (4H, m, aniline-H), 8.45 (1H, s, HC=N)	18.31 (C ₉ -Me, C ₁₃ -Me), 20.69 (C ₁₁ -Me), 117.28-166.31 (aromatic ring carbons), 161.38 (C ₇), 166.60 (C ₂)
(5)	1.20 (12H, d, J 6 Hz, CHMe ₂), 3.02 (4H, sept, J 6 Hz, CHMe ₂), 6.88-7.28 (4H, m, phenolate-H), 7.33-7.60 (3H, m, aniline-H), 8.40 (CH=N)	23.56 (CHMe ₂), 28.01 (CHMe ₂), 117.49-166.3 (aromatic carbons), 161.43 (C ₇), 166.60 (C ₂)
(6)	1.21 (24H, d, J 6 Hz, CHMe ₂), 3.02 (4H, sept, J 6 Hz, CHMe ₂), 6.93-7.33 (8H, m, phenolate-H), 7.37-7.64 (6H, m, aniline-H), 8.40 (2H, s, CH=N)	23.52 (CHMe ₂), 28.12 (CHMe ₂), 117.29-166.66 (aromatic ring carbons), 161.43 (C ₇), 166.60 (C ₂)
(7)	2.19 (6H, s, Me-9,13), 2.32 (3H, s, Me-11), 6.88-7.55 (12H, m, aromatic ring-H), 8.45 (1H, s, CH=N)	18.20 (C ₉ -Me, C ₁₃ -Me), 20.69 (C ₁₁ -Me), 118.10-135.87 (aromatic ring carbons), 141.27 (C ₈), 163.26 (C ₇), 167.02 (C ₂)
(8)	1.16 (12H, s, J 6 Hz, CHMe ₂), 2.95 (2H, sept, J 6 Hz, CHMe ₂), 6.79-7.68 (7H, m, aromatic ring-H), 8.40 (1H, s, CH=N)	23.51 (CHMe ₂), 28.49 (CHMe ₂), 117.82-133.54 (aromatic ring carbons), 138.85 (C ₈), 162.15 (C ₇), 167.18 (C ₂)

some physical data are listed in Table 1.

A solution of pyridine (0.29 g, 3.68 mmol) and $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_2\text{Me}_3\text{-2,4,6}$ (0.88 g, 3.68 mmol) in benzene (~20 ml) was added to GeCl_4 (0.79 g, 3.69 mmol) in benzene (~30 ml) and the resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 11 h. The precipitated $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N.HCl}$ (0.42 g, 3.63 mmol) was removed by filtration. Removal of volatiles from the filtrate under reduced pressure afforded a yellow solid, which was recrystallized from toluene and *n*-hexane mixture at -20°C to obtain the title compound as yellow solid in 1.46 g (95%) yield.

Adopting a procedure similar to **1** derivatives **2**, **3**, and **4**, were prepared using reactants in required quantities as given below for each compound.

- (2) GeCl_4 (0.32 g, 1.49 mmol), $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_2\text{Me}_3\text{-2,4,6}$ (0.71 g, 2.98 mmol) and $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (0.24 g, 2.98 mmol). Precipitated $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N.HCl}$ (in gram) : Found (Calcd.) : 0.31 (0.35).
- (3) GeCl_4 (1.06 g, 1.35 mmol), $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}^i\text{-2,6}$ (1.39 g, 4.95 mmol) and $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (0.40 g, 5.05 mmol). Precipitated $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N.HCl}$ (in gram) : Found (Calcd.) : 0.54 (0.57).
- (4) GeCl_4 (1.15 g, 5.35 mmol), $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}^i\text{-2,6}$ (2.99 g, 10.63 mmol) and $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (0.89 g, 11.27 mmol). Precipitated $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N.HCl}$ (in gram) : Found (Calcd.) : 1.21 (1.23).

A tetrahydrofuran (~20 ml) solution of $\text{NaOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_2\text{Me}_3\text{-2,4,6}$ [freshly prepared by the equimolar interaction of Na (0.22 g, 9.89 mg atom) and Schiff base (2.31 g, 9.65 mmol) in THF] was added to a solution of SnCl_4 (1.27 g, 4.88 mmol) in benzene (~20 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h, followed by refluxing for ~9 h. The precipitated NaCl (0.56 g, 9.58 mmol) was separated by filtration. Volatiles from the filtrate were removed under reduced pressure to obtain the title compound as a yellow solid (3.10 g). The product was purified by recrystallization from a mixture of toluene and *n*-hexane at -20°C in ~80% yield.

Complexes **5**, **7** and **8** were prepared by a similar procedure as described for **6**. The quantities of the reactants used and precipitated NaCl in each case are given below :

- (5) SnCl_4 (2.06 g, 7.91 mmol) and $\text{NaOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_2\text{Me}_3\text{-2,4,6}$ [prepared from $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_2\text{Me}_3\text{-2,4,6}$ (1.87 g, 7.83 mmol) and Na (0.18

g, 8.08 mg atom) in THF]. Precipitated NaCl (in gram) : Found (Calcd.) : 0.44 (0.45).

- (7) SnCl_4 (1.43 g, 5.50 mmol) and $\text{NaOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_2\text{Pr}^i\text{-2,6}$ [prepared from $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_2\text{Pr}^i\text{-2,4,6}$ (1.54 g, 5.46 mmol) and Na (0.13 g, 5.61 mg atom) in THF]. Precipitated NaCl (in gram) : Found (Calcd.) : 0.31 (0.32).
- (8) SnCl_4 (0.67 g, 2.57 mmol) and $\text{NaOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_2\text{Me}_3\text{-2,6}$ [prepared from $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_2\text{Me}_3\text{-2,4,6}$ (1.42 g, 5.052 mmol) and Na (0.12 g, 5.14 mg atom) in THF]. Precipitated NaCl (in gram) : Found (Calcd.) : 0.28 (0.29).

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References

1. (a) R. H. Holm, G. W. Everett (Jr.) and A. Chakravorty, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **7**, 83; (b) M. D. Hobday and T. D. Smith, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **9**, 311; (c) S. Yamada, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 415; (d) R. C. Mehrotra, G. Srivastava and B. S. Saraswat, *Revs. Si, Ge, Sn, Pb Compounds*, 1982, **6**, 171; (e) J. C. G. Bunzli and D. Wessner, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1984, **60**, 191; (f) D. E. Fenton and P. A. Vigato, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1988, **17**, 69; (g) M. Nath and M. Goyal, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 1996, **19**, 75; (h) S. Yamada, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1999, **192**, 557; (i) L. Canali and D. C. Sherrington, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1999, **28**, 85; (j) A. D. Garnovskii, A. L. Nivorozhkin and V. I. Minkin, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **126**, 1.
2. (a) S. Goyal and A. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 638; (b) M. Goyal, S. Mishra and A. Singh, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 2001, **24**, 829; (c) M. Goyal, S. Mishra and A. Singh, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2001, **175**, 143; (d) M. Goyal, S. Mishra and A. Singh, *Synth. React. Metal-Organic Chem.*, 2001, **31**, 1705; (e) S. Goyal and A. Singh, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-organ. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 1133; (f) S. Mishra, M. Goyal and A. Singh, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 2002, **25**, 437; (g) R. S. Ghadwal, M. Sharma, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2004, **29**, 419; (h) S. Mishra and A. Singh, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2004, **29**, 164; (i) S. Bansal, Y. P. Singh and A. Singh, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 2005, **28**, 149; (j) R. S. Ghadwal, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2005, **30**, 268; (k) N. B. Sharma and A. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2006, **45**, 2638; (l) N. B. Sharma and A. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 658; (m) N. B. Sharma, S. Bansal, Y. P. Singh and A. Singh, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 2005, **28**, 149; (n) N. B. Sharma and A. Singh, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2007, **182**, 15.

3. See for example : C. M. Che and J. S. Huang, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **242**, 97 and references therein.
4. J. P. Taquet, O. Siri, P. Braunstein and R. Welter, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 6944 and references therein; (b) T. R. Younkin, E. F. Connor, J. I. Henderson, S. K. Friedrich, R. H. Grubbs and D. A. Bansleben, *Science*, 2000, **288**, 1750; (c) C. Carlini, A. M. Raspolli Galletti and G. Sbrana, *Polymer*, 2003, **44**, 1995; (d) C. Carlini, M. Isola, V. Liuzzo, A. M. Raspolli Galletti and G. Sbrana, *Appl. Catal. (A)*, 2002, **231**, 307; (e) M. Pickel, T. Casper, A. Rahm, C. Dambouwy and P. Chen, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 2002, **85**, 4337.
5. Y. Wang, J. L. Dubois, B. Hedman, K. O. Hodgson and T. D. P. Stack, *Science*, 1998, **279**, 537.
6. S. Goyal, S. Mishra and A. Singh, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 2001, **24**, 413.
7. See for example : D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra, I. P. Rothwell and A. Singh, "Alkoxo and Aryloxo Derivatives of Metals", Academic Press, London, 2001.
8. (a) K. Sharma, N. B. Sharma and A. Singh, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2006, **181**, 2735; (b) N. B. Sharma, J. Shahani and A. Singh, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 2006, **29**, 107.
9. G. A. Miller and E. O. Schlemper, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, **30**, 131.
10. (a) A. Jain, S. Saxena and A. K. Rai, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 1993, **16**, 223; (b) M. Biesemans, R. Willem, S. Bamoun, P. Geerlings, E. R. T. Tiekink, P. Jaumier, M. Lahcini and B. Jousseume, *Organometallics*, 1998, **17**, 90.